

NOTES

metal chelates was found to be $\text{Pr}^{3+} < \text{Nd}^{3+} < \text{Sm}^{3+} < \text{Gd}^{3+} < \text{Dy}^{3+}$.

Experimental

The ligand, N-4-acylacenaphthylidene-*o*-aminophenol (I), was synthesized and identified as reported earlier^{1,2}. Rare earth chlorides, either taken directly (PrCl_3 , NdCl_3 or DyCl_3) or obtained from oxides (Sm_2O_3 or Gd_2O_3) were made anhydrous³. Appropriate amounts of these rare earth chlorides were dissolved in perchloric acid to prevent the hydrolysis of these ions. The solution of ligand was prepared in ethanol. NaOH (B.D.H.), NaClO_4 (Riedel) and HClO_4 (E. Merck) solutions were prepared in CO_2 free double distilled water. NaOH and HClO_4 solutions were standardised by standard method⁴.

A Philips pH-meter, PP 9040 fitted with combination electrode single rod assembly PV 9014 (accuracy 0.1 pH) was used for pH measurement. The apparatus was standardised against 0.05 M potassium hydrogenphthalate for pH 4 in 80% (v/v) aq. ethanol medium at $30 \pm 1^\circ$. The pH titrations of the following mixtures were performed against 0.1 M NaOH at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ maintaining the ionic strength $\mu = 0.1$ M (NaClO_4) and total volume 50 ml.

- 5 ml HClO_4 (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO_4 (1 M) + 40 ml water.
- 5 ml HClO_4 (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO_4 (1 M) + 25 ml (0.005 M) ligand + 15 ml water.
- 5 ml HClO_4 (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO_4 (1 M) + 25 ml (0.005 M) ligand + 5 ml metal (0.005 M) + 10 ml water.

The ratio of metal reagent concentration was kept at 1 : 5 to satisfy the highest coordination number of the metal. The above three mixtures were titrated separately adding NaOH progressively with constant stirring (magnetic stirrer) and the pH values were recorded.

Results and Discussion

The ligand being monoprotic, neutralizes one equivalent of base to give one buffer region in its titration curve. Values of formation function $\bar{n}A$ (the average number of protons attached per ligand molecule), \bar{n} (the average number of ligand ions attached per metal ion) and pL (free ligand exponent) were calculated using the Irving and Rossotti equations⁵. The protonation constant of the ligand ($\log K_1^H$) and stepwise stability constant of metal-ligand, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated using the half integral method, least square method and pointwise calculation method. The values are

in good agreement with each other and the average values are reported in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

	Temp. $30 \pm 1^\circ$					
	$\mu = 0.1$ M (NaClO_4)					
	H ⁺	Pr ³⁺	Nd ³⁺	Sm ³⁺	Gd ³⁺	Dy ³⁺
log K ₁	9.68	6.40	6.53	7.05	7.13	7.35
log K ₂	—	6.14	6.97	6.70	6.78	7.21

* For proton association (H⁺), K₁ corresponds to the species LH, while for the metal ions K₁ and K₂ corresponds to the species ML and ML₂, respectively.

The maximum value of \bar{n} obtained in the pH region where hydrolysis of metal ion was negligible was between 1.5 and 2.0. This indicates the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes. The order of stability of the trivalent metal chelates was found to $\text{Pr}^{3+} < \text{Nd}^{3+} < \text{Sm}^{3+} < \text{Gd}^{3+} < \text{Dy}^{3+}$. The increase in stabilities of rare earth metal complexes with decrease in ionic or crystal radii indicates the absence of extensive covalent bonding due to non-availability of 4f electrons for bond formation.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to the University Grant Commission, New Delhi for financial assistance.

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Stability Constants of N-4-Methylphenacylidene-anthranilic Acid Complexes with Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Cd^{2+}

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Manuscript received 26 February 1982, accepted 29 December 1982

ACID dissociation constant of N-4-methylphenacylidene-anthranilic acid and the stability constants of its metal chelates with various bivalent metal ions have been determined in 75% (v/v) dioxane-water mixture at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ and constant ionic strength $\mu = 0.1$ M (NaClO_4) by adopting the pH titration technique of Irving and Rossotti. The stability constants follow the Irving-William's order.

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Experimental

All the chemicals used were of G. R. or A. R. grade. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was used to maintain the ionic strength constant. The dioxane used for experimental work was purified¹.

The ligand, 4-methylphenacylidene anthranilic acid (I), was prepared by refluxing equimolar amounts of 4-methylphenylglyoxalhydrate with anthranilic acid in ethanol on a steam bath for 3.5 hr. The reaction mixture was refrigerated and the solid product obtained was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol (m.p. 190°). Satisfactory elemental analysis were obtained.

The stock solutions of NaClO_4 , HClO_4 and NaOH were prepared in usual manner in double distilled water. All pH measurements were carried out on a Philips PP 9040 pH meter fitted with combination electrode single rod assembly PV 9014 (accuracy 0.1 pH). The instrument was standardised against 0.05 M solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate for pH 4. Following solutions were titrated separately against standard NaOH (0.1 M) at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ (i) free HClO_4 , (ii) free HClO_4 + ligand and (iii) metal-perchlorate in free HClO_4 + ligand. The ratio between the metal and the ligand was kept at 1 : 4 and the ionic strength of 0.1 M was maintained with appropriate amount of 1M NaClO_4 .

Results and Discussion

From the pH titration curves, the values $\bar{n}A$, \bar{n} and pL were obtained adopting the Irving-Rossotti technique². From the titration curves of solutions (i) and (ii), $\bar{n}A$ values at various pH values were calculated. The formation curve was plotted between $\bar{n}A$ and pH extending over a range $0.35 > \bar{n}A > 0.90$. This indicates the formation of species HL only. The value of pK_1^H was evaluated from the half integral point $\bar{n}A = 0.5$. From the straight line plot of $\log \left(\frac{\bar{n}A}{1 - \bar{n}A} \right)$ against pH, the pK_1^H was also determined. This value agrees with that obtained by half integral method.

The maximum value of \bar{n} obtained in the pH region where hydrolysis of metal ions is negligible is between 1.5 and 2.0 and revealed that metal-ligand ratio in the complexes is 1 : 2. The metal ligand stability constants were obtained from the formation curves (\bar{n} and pL), by plotting pL vs $\log \left(\frac{1 - \bar{n}}{\bar{n}} \right)$ for $\log K_1$ and pL vs $\log \left(\frac{2 - \bar{n}}{\bar{n} - 1} \right)$ for $\log K_2$. Log K values are given in Table 1 and follows the order $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Cd}^{2+}$ in agreement with Irving-Williams order³.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES*

	Temp. $30 \pm 1^\circ$					
	$\mu = 0.1 \text{ M (NaClO}_4\text{)}$					
	H^+	Cu^{2+}	Zn^{2+}	Ni^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Cd^{2+}
$\log K_1$	4.37	9.56	8.55	7.68	7.51	7.21
$\log K_2$	—	4.80	4.23	3.27	3.12	3.05

* For H^+ , K_1 corresponds to the species LH, while for metal ions K_1 and K_2 corresponds to species ML and ML_2 , respectively.

The complexation reactions are as follows :

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to the University Grants Commission, New Delhi for financial assistance.

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Spectrophotometric Studies on Dimethyl Tin Dichloride with PAN, Quinalizarin, Alizarin Red S, Solochrome Black and Methyl Oxine

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Manuscript received 3 March 1982, revised 16 August 1982, accepted 28 December 1982

THE composition, structure and stability constants of many chelates have been determined by using mole ratio method, Job's method of continuous variation and slope ratio method. Pilloni¹, on the basis of spectrophotometric measurements, concluded complexation between PAN and a few organo-metallic moieties such as $\text{R}_2\text{Sn(II)}$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Pb(II)}$ in dioxane. Many authors²⁻⁴ have done a number of similar studies in the recent past.

The present work was undertaken to extend the above investigations using following systems in 95% ethanol as a solvent.

Systems :

1. $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and 1-(2-pyridylazo)-2-naphthol (PAN).
2. $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and 1,2,5,8-tetrahydroxy anthraquinone (Quinalizarin).
3. $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2$ and 1,2-dihydroxy-3-anthraquinone sulphonic acid-Na Salt (Alizarin red S).

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